

The Influence of Socio-Economic Status on Malaria Treatment in Municipal Local Government Area of Kano State, Nigeria: A Public Opinion Survey

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Abstract

This study explores socio-economic status and perceived treatment of malaria within the Municipal Local Government Area of Kano State. Its objectives are to: examine public opinion regarding how socio-economic status influences malaria treatment in the Municipal Local Government Area; explore different treatment options for malaria infection; and investigate the factors that affect the choice of effective malaria treatments in the area. The study uses a descriptive survey design with a multistage systematic random sampling method to select 400 participants, based on the Taro Yamane formula and a total population of 969. Questionnaires were given to adult males and females who have used any malaria treatment and reside within Kano Municipal. The data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 23 with descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages, presented in tables. Results indicate that socio-economic factors like income, education, and residence (ecology) significantly influence the types of malaria treatment used. Treatment options include orthodox medication, especially Artemisinin-based Combination Therapy (ACT), traditional medicines, and self-medication, reflecting medical pluralism. Factors such as income level and medication cost also influence treatment choices. The study concludes that socio-economic aspects such as income, occupation, proximity or access to healthcare, and cultural beliefs or knowledge about the nature, causes, and understanding of malaria affect treatment decisions. There are three main malaria treatment options: traditional, orthodox, and dual methods. Ultimately, cultural beliefs, medication costs, income levels, referrals, and knowledge are key factors shaping treatment choices for malaria.

Keywords: *Malaria Illness, Malaria Treatment, Public Opinion, and Socio-economic Status.*

Introduction

Malaria is a serious health challenge to most communities in Nigeria, and it has been a part and parcel of the existential health problems for many years. Traditional and orthodox medications for malaria have been provided, but it still stands the test of time as one of the most prevalent diseases affecting Nigerians. It is an endemic illness that is inflicting diverse degrees of discomfort, pain, and even resulting in deaths of mostly children under 5 years old and adults mostly in the suburbs (Alwar, 2020). In sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where there is a high prevalence of malaria illness resulting from paucity of basic amenities of life coupled with poor socio-economic conditions, poor environmental sanitary practices, and cultural description of developing societies (Amzat & Razum, 2014), like Nigeria. The World Health Organization (WHO) noted that malaria is a severe human disease that causes fever, which is contracted through the bite of female Anopheles mosquitoes (Alwar, 2020; World Health Organization, 2023).

Malaria symptoms include high body temperature with fever, cold, perspiration, severe headache, and poor appetite for food, which, if not diagnosed and treated in time, may lead to death. However, the incidence of socio-economic disparities in Africa can significantly impact access to health care services vis-a-vis health-seeking behaviour, knowledge, and awareness of malaria prevention/treatment, causing delays in healthcare (Ajimotokan, 2023). The high rate of underdevelopment and poverty (Amzat & Razum, 2014; WHO, 2022) has had significant effects on the social and economic decisions that most families make in Nigeria. These adverse socio-economic conditions within any community or nation can impede the health and prosperity of individuals and society as a whole. The possibility of contracting malaria in endemic areas can discourage investment from both domestic and foreign sources, potentially leading to a range of negative effects on households and individual decision-making, which can hinder economic growth and productivity due to the prevalence and fear of the illness. Thus, the scourge of malaria impedes people's social and economic development by causing prolonged health damage in addition to being absent from work or school, as well as other social and economic activities.

However, the World Health Organization (2023) found that low educational attainment or lack of health awareness increases people's vulnerability to copious severe diseases, including malaria infection. The organization maintains that, due to the inability of low-income families to access necessary information about public health (Vega, 2019), as well as the use of insecticide-treated bed nets (ITN), which is a suitable means of malaria prevention technique given that it is flexible, accessible, and pocket-friendly to all. Moreover, mosquitoes that are vectors of malaria illness usually find poorly sanitized environments most conducive for breeding, and as such, increase the chance of transmitting the disease to the inhabitants of the place. This is perhaps why malaria illness has been conveniently described as an "environmental" illness (Madobi, 2019).

It can be inferred from the foregoing that malaria is one of the most prevalent public health issues in Nigeria (CDC, 2021; WHO, 2019). Despite the associated scare imposed by this deadly illness, individuals with malaria in Nigeria and other sub-Saharan African nations find it difficult to access healthcare services due to the high cost of treatment at the formal healthcare centre. Similarly, the cost of treatment of malaria can be more devastating for some households than others, especially as low-income families suffer more from the burden of financial cost of malaria treatment as they spend a larger proportion of their income in the course of seeking malaria treatment. The impact of malaria treatment cost becomes more significant when one considers the recurring nature of malaria in individuals in endemic countries in a year (Anyanwu, 2017), as well as the estimated cost being expended persistently in the course of treating the disease. The costs encompass a range of expenses, such as purchasing a hospital hand card, consultation fee, essential medications, laboratory investigations and tests, transport fare, and others.

Although Nigeria bears a significant burden of malaria cases, with a high prevalence in many regions, including Kano State, particularly Kano Municipal LGA, a densely populated area within the state, experiences a substantial

number of malaria cases (Sato, 2021) annually. This is very common during the wet season, which is the peak period of malaria infestation in the state. As such, understanding the influence of socio-economic status on malaria treatment is crucial for developing effective strategies to combat the illness and improve overall health outcomes. The best way of understanding the influence is by aggregating the opinion of the actors in the study. It is on the above background that the paper seeks to achieve the following objectives.

- i. To examine public response on the influence of socio-economic status on the treatment of malaria in the Municipal Local Government Area in Kano state.
- ii. To explore the various treatment options for malaria illness in the Municipal Local Government Area in Kano state.
- iii. To investigate the possible factors that influence the choice of treatment options for malaria illness in the study area.

Related Literature

Malaria is a life-threatening disease caused by protozoan parasites belonging to the genus *Plasmodium*, which are transmitted to humans through the bites of infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes (Liu et al, 2020). Despite significant advances in public health, malaria remains one of the most widespread infectious diseases globally, affecting millions of individuals each year, primarily in subtropical and tropical regions. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2022), there were an estimated 241 million cases of malaria worldwide in 2020, leading to approximately 627,000 deaths, with the majority of cases concentrated in sub-Saharan Africa. Children under the age of five and pregnant women are particularly vulnerable to severe malaria complications, resulting in high morbidity and mortality rates in these populations (Baird, 2019). Several factors, including climate, population movement, and socio-economic conditions influence malaria transmission patterns.

The treatment of malaria is primarily dependent on the *Plasmodium* species and the severity of the disease. For uncomplicated cases of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria, Artemisinin-based Combination Therapies (ACTs) are recommended, which combine an Artemisinin derivative with a longer-acting partner drug to enhance efficacy and reduce the risk of resistance (WHO, 2021). Severe malaria requires prompt treatment with intravenous Artesunate. In addition to antimalarial medications, supportive care and management of complications are critical for improving patient outcomes (Kakkar et al., 2021).

Socio-economic status is a multifaceted construct encompassing income, education, and occupation, which collectively shape individuals' and communities' access to healthcare services. Individuals from lower SES backgrounds often face significant barriers in accessing malaria treatment. These barriers include inadequate healthcare infrastructure, financial constraints, and transportation challenges. For example, rural populations may

reside far from healthcare facilities that offer malaria treatment, leading to delays in seeking care (Munyeki et al., 2021). Conversely, those with higher SES are typically better able to afford medical expenses and reach healthcare facilities promptly, resulting in better health outcomes (Thwing & Garbus, 2014).

Socio-economic inequalities directly affect the management of malaria, creating a vicious cycle of poverty and poor health. Regions with high malaria prevalence often correlate with lower SES indicators, such as low household income, underemployment, and limited education opportunities. According to Nnko et al. (2018), children and pregnant women living in impoverished conditions are among the most vulnerable to malaria and its complications due to inadequate access to preventive measures such as insecticide-treated nets and prophylactic medications. In contrast, individuals from higher SES backgrounds typically reside in areas with better sanitation and housing conditions, which reduce mosquito breeding sites and exposure to malaria vectors. Health interventions tailored to high SES populations, such as indoor residual spraying and accessible healthcare services, tend to yield better results in malaria treatment outcomes (Bousema et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the availability of essential medications plays a crucial role in treating malaria effectively. The World Health Organization (2021) estimates that in low-income countries, access to antimalarial medicines can be inconsistent, often due to supply chain issues, economic instability, and corruption. Those in higher SES brackets often have greater access to quality medicines and healthcare services. In contrast, marginalized groups may resort to self-treatment, which can exacerbate drug resistance and treatment failure (Owusu-Agyei et al., 2018).

There are two major pathways (channels) in seeking for malaria treatment, which are orthodox and traditional healthcare systems (Julie et al, 2020; Zakariyya, 2023). However, the primary approach to treating malaria is the use of antimalarial medications. The choice of medication depends on various factors, including the species of *Plasmodium*, the severity of the disease, and the patient's age and health status.

ACTs are the recommended first-line treatment for uncomplicated malaria caused by *Plasmodium (P) falciparum*, the most lethal malaria species. These combinations enhance efficacy and reduce the risk of resistance. Common ACTs include artemether-lumefantrine (Coartem) and artesunate-amodiaquine (Katenjeva) (WHO, 2022). Studies have shown that ACTs significantly reduce mortality and morbidity associated with malaria (Dondorp et al., 2010). Chloroquine was once the cornerstone of malaria treatment but has fallen out of favor in many areas due to widespread resistance among *Plasmodium falciparum* populations. However, it remains effective against *Plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium ovale*. In regions without resistance, chloroquine is a cost-effective option (Kumar et al., 2019).

Quinine is an older antimalarial drug that has shown effectiveness against severe malaria but is often associated with significant side effects, including cinchonism and hypoglycemia. As a result, it is typically used in combination therapies or when other options are unavailable (Price et al., 2014). Other medications include primaquine, which

is effective against *P. vivax* and important for preventing relapses, and mefloquine, which is used in some cases, particularly where resistance to other treatments is noted (Halberstadt et al., 2021). tafenoquine, another new drug approved for the radical cure of *P. vivax*, is gaining traction as it requires a single dose (O'Neil et al., 2017).

In addition to antimalarial drugs, supportive care is essential, particularly for severe cases of malaria. This includes: Intravenous fluids are essential for maintaining hydration and correcting electrolyte imbalances (WHO, 2022). The RTS, S/AS01 (Mosquirix) malaria vaccine has shown moderate efficacy in preventing malaria among young children in endemic regions. While it is not a treatment option per se, its use can complement existing treatment strategies, reducing the overall burden of malaria (WHO, 2021).

A combination of biological, economic, social, and healthcare system factors influences the choice of treatment for malaria. First, the species of *Plasmodium* (P) infecting the individual is the most significant determinant of treatment choice. *P. falciparum*, known for its resistance to many drugs, necessitates the use of ACTs in most regions. In contrast, infections with *P. vivax* may involve the use of primaquine to prevent relapses, depending on the patient's G6PD status to avoid hemolytic anemia (WHO, 2022). Resistance patterns are continually changing, and surveillance must inform treatment guidelines (Babiker et al., 2020).

Second, the severity of malaria determines the treatment approach. Severe cases often require parenteral administration of Artesunate at a healthcare facility, while mild cases can be treated with oral medications at home. The need for hospitalization influences the resources allocated to malaria treatment (Gimmig et al., 2020). The availability of healthcare resources, including laboratory facilities for malaria diagnosis and essential medications, greatly influences treatment choices. In low-resource settings, accessible and cost-effective treatments like chloroquine may be favored despite potential resistance (Munyeki et al., 2021). Healthcare providers' training and the presence of community health workers can also guide treatment decisions (Khan et al., 2020). Third, Economic factors play a crucial role in treatment choices. In low-income areas, the cost of medications can limit access to effective treatments. The affordability of ACTs versus cheaper but less effective drugs may lead healthcare personnel to opt for cheaper alternatives, which may not provide the best outcomes in areas of resistance (Birkhead et al., 2019). Availability of subsidized medications from public health programs also affects treatment adherence and choice.

Finally, Cultural beliefs and health-seeking behaviors influence treatment choices. In some settings, traditional medicine may be preferred over conventional medical treatments, affecting adherence to prescribed antimalarial. Stigmas or misconceptions about modern medicine can lead to underutilization of effective treatments (Mok et al., 2020). Malaria remains a pressing global health challenge, and various factors, including the type of *Plasmodium* species, the severity of illness, healthcare infrastructure, economic factors, and sociocultural context shape the treatment landscape. As treatment options evolve, understanding these influencing factors is critical for effective malaria management and for tailoring interventions to meet the needs of affected populations.

Theoretical Framework

Three Delay Model

This theoretical model was developed by Thaddeus and Maine (1994) as an approach to address each of the issues a person battling a disease (such as malaria) faces in the course of approaching a health care facility. However, the model emphasized that lack of economic and human resources does not always result in morbidity and mortality but could result in delay for health care, which in the long run could increase the chances of recording casualties. Accordingly, Thaddeus and Maine (1994) identified three types of delays as the major causes of complications from certain illnesses like malaria. The delays are in three phases as presented below:

i. Seeking Care: This delay happens as a result of the decision-making on the best available and affordable health care services to the victim of malaria and the significant other. These significant others include home health givers and family members. This is after the decision is made on the appropriate health care, which is further influenced by the income, accessibility, and affordability of health care services, and previous experience on the perceived pathway to health used. The second phase could further delay this as the sick person has made a decision and is trying to access the health care service.

ii. Reaching Care: Several socio-economic factors—such as income level, accessibility, means of transportation, and proximity to healthcare—can contribute to additional delays in reaching the designated healthcare facility. Here, delay in terms of proximity, transportation, and timing will serve as obstacles in reaching the health care. Proximity in terms of how close and accessible the health care centre is. Predominantly, those in outskirts areas of the metropolis suffer more due to the distance to be covered to gain access to tertiary orthodox health services. Also, one concerning aspect is not having the personal means of transporting themselves to the health service facilities in time, and even worse, locating public transportation services can be very difficult in most cases. Finally, whether the illness attacks at night or day is also a factor that determines access to the health service. Mostly at night, mobility is minimal, especially on the verge of security challenges, which present another layer of obstacles. After overcoming these stages of delays, upon arrival at the hospital, the final delay is expected to be overcome to have the desired health care delivery.

iii. Receiving (Appropriate) Care: Here, significant logistics delay sets in. The delay in getting all the front-end or basic aspects of hospital consultation, like getting and paying for consultancy cards/charges, availability of the doctor on call, attitude of some hospital personnel, routine clinical examination, and administration of medication. These are some of the delays that affect malaria treatment and are mostly tied to socio-economic impediments of the victim and significant other.

The three-delay model was adopted in this study to explain why some patients or significant others experience delay in seeking malaria medication due to their socio-economic status in society. According to the model, during a

malaria illness episode, many people are involved in the decision-making process and is based on the level of income, proximity to care, and knowledge of the nature of the disease by the patient/significant other which constitutes a web of delays that can aggravate malaria illness amongst the sick (Vamos, 2020).

Methodology

The research design is a descriptive survey, and the primary data collection method used was a questionnaire. The self-administered questionnaires were distributed over three months, from August 2024 to November 2024. The population of the Municipal local government is estimated at 969 with a growth rate of 2.5% per year [National Population Commission (NPC), 2022]. However, the study's working population included both male and female adults from all economic, socio-cultural, and religious backgrounds residing in the Municipal. A sample size of approximately 400 was determined using Taro Yamane's (1967) formula. The respondent selection process employed a multistage sampling technique involving four stages due to the large, dispersed population across several political wards. First, the metropolis was divided according to its 13 political wards. Second, four wards- Yakasai, Gandun Albas, Sheshe, and Zaitawa- were selected through simple random sampling using a lottery method, representing at least one-third of the total wards. Third, each of the four selected wards was allocated a sample of 100 respondents. Finally, systematic random sampling via the nth household method (selecting the 5th household in each street) was used to administer questionnaires to individual households within each ward until the required sample size was reached. Data collection was carried out using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. Quantitative Data were analyzed with SPSS version 23, and results were presented in tables showing frequency distributions and percentages.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Showing Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Frequency (n=400)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>Age</i>		
18-24	42	11
25-34	119	30
35-44	142	36
45-54	54	13
44-64	26	6
65 and older	17	4
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	235	58
Female	165	42
<i>Marital status</i>		
Single	21	5
Married	218	55
Divorced	17	4
Widow	144	36
<i>Total</i>	400	100

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2024

The above Table 1 shows socio-demographic data of the research participants, the first data was on the age and out of 400 respondents, 11% belong to the age group of 18-24 years, while 30% belong to the age group of 25-34 years, 36% belong to age group of 35-44 years, 13% belong to the 45-54, 6% belong to the age group of 55-64 and 4% belong to the age group of 65 and older respectively. This is an indication that the majority of the respondents were within the age group of 25-44 years. This implies that respondents were adults within the working ages, which confirmed the study area description and characteristics of the study population.

Also, Table 1 reveals the distribution of the respondents by gender, 58% out of 400 respondents were male, while 42% were female. The data indicates that the majority of the respondents were male; this is because there were more male respondents in the study area than females.

The marital status of respondents was also investigated. The findings indicate that out of the total respondents, 55% were married, 36% were widows, 4% were divorced, while 5% were single. This could be as a result of the norms of Hausa people that promote marriage when one reaches 25years of age and above and has the capability of doing so.

RQ 1: Examine Public responses on the influence of socio-economic status on the treatment of malaria in the Municipal local government area in Kano state

Table 2: Public responses on the influence of socio-economic status and malaria treatment of the study participants

Construct	Strongly agreed		Agreed		Strongly disagreed		Disagreed		Undecided		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
<i>The fear of cost of treatment (due to income level of respondent) in modern healthcare facility influences negatively on malaria treatment</i>	284	71	73	18.25	20	5	14	3.5	9	2.25	400	100
<i>Nature of occupation and time of respondent negatively influenced malaria treatment.</i>	238	59.5	113	28.25	22	5.5	12	3	15	3.75	400	100
<i>Malaria illness increases due to delay prompt decision to seek for health care negatively influence malaria treatment</i>	256	64	119	29.75	11	2.75	7	1.75	7	1.75	400	100
<i>Level of awareness and past experiences on malaria affect the use of malaria treatment options</i>	230	57.5	128	32	22	5.5	8	2	12	3	400	100
<i>Inaccessibility to healthcare centre is the reason for delay in seeking malaria treatment</i>	214	53.5	128	32	30	7.5	16	4	12	3	400	100

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2024.

As shown in Table 2 above, the most significant response showed that (71%; 284) respondents strongly agree that they experience delay in seeking for malaria medication due to the cost of treatment while the least significant

response indicated that only (2.25%; 9) remained unanimous. This is an indication that many people experience a delay in going for malaria medication due to the cost of medication that their level of income can preclude.

The study also found that the most significant response (59.5%; 238) of respondents strongly agreed that the nature of the occupation caused the delay, while the least significant response (3%; 12) showed that only a few respondents disagreed with the delay caused by the nature of work. This implies that a job that is time demanding and highly task demanding has a greater influence on prompt access to health care services.

Furthermore, a significant number of respondents (64%; 256) strongly agreed that delays were caused by the inability to make quicker decisions regarding the necessary and appropriate healthcare regimen for the illness episode. In contrast, the least significant response indicated that only (1.75%; 7) disagreed or remained neutral on the issue of decision-making as a source of delay in prompt healthcare. This suggests that respondents face challenges in making faster decisions to access prompt healthcare services. These challenges are attributed to factors such as available money, caregivers' decisions, previous experiences, and the most suitable treatment options for the sick person's significant others.

In addition, the most significant response of (57.5%; 230) respondents in the sample strongly agreed to the idea that the level of awareness and experience of malaria illness and treatment influences prompt health care services, while the least significant response of (2%; 8) disagree that the level of awareness and experience of malaria illness and treatment has no significant influence in prompt health care services.

Lastly, the most significant response indicates that (53.5%; 214) respondents strongly believed that inaccessibility to healthcare centre is the major cause of delay in seeking malaria treatment whereas the least significant response shows that (3%; 12) of the respondents remained unanimous to the idea of inaccessibility to healthcare centres is the major cause of delay in seeking malaria treatment. This implies that distance is one of the major factors influencing access to healthcare services and health-seeking behaviour regarding malaria treatment in the study area.

The above data presented in Table 2 shows that; public responses on socio-economic status and malaria treatment are: cost of preferred medication based on the income of respondents, proximity to healthcare service that could provide cure, existing cultural experience on the malaria episode, perception and belief of such illness, inaccessibility to prompt healthcare due to the nature of jobs are major causes of negative influence to prompt medical care by the sick attributed to their socio-economic status from the study area.

RQ 2: Explore the various treatment options for malaria illness in the Municipal local government area in Kano state

Table 3: Malaria Treatment Options (Pathways) for Malaria Illness

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Strongly agreed</i>		<i>Agreed</i>		<i>Strongly disagreed</i>		<i>Disagreed</i>		<i>Undecided</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Orthodox medication</i>	281	70.25	73	18.25	17	4.25	8	2	21	5.25	400	100
<i>Traditional medication</i>	198	49.5	100	25	37	9.25	37	9.25	28	7	400	100
<i>Dual-medication</i>	230	57.5	124	31	17	4.25	17	4.25	12	3	400	100

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2024.

As shown in Table 3 above a significant number of the (70.25%; 281) strongly agreed to orthodox medication such as, ACT, hospital care, chemist store medication and home medical consultation as preferred way of treating malaria illness, others (2%; 8) disagreed with orthodox treatments as a viable option to malaria treatment in the study area. The findings imply that sick person in conjunction with care givers believe that Artemisinin-based Combination Therapy (ACT), hospital care, patent store and home orthodox treatments are the most appropriate and effective ways of treating malaria illness in the first attempt and thus, most important treatment options to malaria infection in the study area.

Also, Table 3 shows that (49.5%; 198) out of the sampled respondents strongly agreed to the efficacy and use of traditional and alternative medicines in the cure of malaria illness, while (7%; 27) of them were undecided on the issue of the use of ethno-medicine in the treatment of malaria in the study area. This implies that nearly half of the sampled respondents prefer non-orthodox medicine when seeking malaria treatment in the first attempt thus seeing traditional medication as another possible pathway to malaria treatment in the study area.

However, (57.5%; 230) respondents strongly agreed to have used dual medication which most at times involve a combination of both pathways (orthodox and traditional medicines) in curing malaria to the least significant response of (3%; 12) who were unanimous to the dual-medication prospect in managing malaria in the study area. This implies that the majority of the research participants combines both pathways to healthcare in curing malaria illness when sick.

The above data as presented shows that the study population has varieties of pathways in which treatment of malaria is been sourced. These treatment options ranges from orthodox, traditional and the mixture of both as the case may be. Factors like cultural belief, subjective perception of the illness episode, availability and proximity to immediate health care service, available financial resources and cost of medication as triggers and measurement strand to the option of any medication used in treating malaria in the area.

RQ 3: Investigate the possible factors that influencing the choice of malaria treatment in the municipal local government area in Kano state.

Table 4: Possible Factors that influencing the Choice of Malaria Treatment

Source: Researchers’ Survey, 2024

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Strongly agreed</i>		<i>Agreed</i>		<i>Strongly disagreed</i>		<i>Disagreed</i>		<i>Undecided</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Cost of medication</i>	297	74.25	81	20.25	9	2.25	8	2	5	1.25	400	100
<i>Proximity to care</i>	288	72	56	14	10	2.5	30	7.5	16	4	400	100
<i>Cultural belief</i>	199	49.75	98	24.5	11	2.75	75	18.75	17	4.25	400	100
<i>Family preferences</i>	29	7.25	27	6.75	192	48	113	28.25	39	9.75	400	100
<i>Level of income</i>	238	59.5	128	32	12	3	22	5.5	-	-	400	100

Table 4 above displays participants' responses on whether the cost of medication affects one's choice of treating malaria illness, where the most significant number of respondents (74.25%; 297) strongly agreed that the cost of medication influences the choice for malaria treatment and affordability. This is compared to (1.25; 5) who were undecided in their stand on the cost of medication influencing the choice for malaria treatment. This implies that the cost of medication significantly affects the health-seeking behaviour of the participants in relation to malaria treatment and pathways to health.

Also, Table 4 shows that; the most significant response of (72%; 288) indicates respondents who strongly agreed that proximity and accessibility to healthcare greatly influenced the choice of healthcare, while (2.5%; 10) of the respondents strongly disagreed that proximity plays a significant role in the choice of healthcare towards malaria treatment in the study area. This implies that, the closeness and easy accessibility to healthcare facilities and its patronage promotes quick and easy choice of healthcare while the longer distance and inaccessibility to healthcare prevents its choice as a viable healthcare option to the treatment of malaria in the study area.

More so, the table 4 also showed that (49.75%; 199) of the respondents strongly agreed to the idea of cultural belief on the perceived nature, causes and ontology of the malaria illness episode influences the treatment option and necessary pathway to health care, (2.75; 11) of them strongly disagreed to the stand that cultural belief on the perceived nature, causes and ontology of the malaria illness episode influences the treatment option and necessary pathway to health care. This implies that, cultural belief has a significant influence in the treatment option used in treating malaria illness in the study area.

However, family preference is not found to be a significant factor that influences one's choice of treating malaria illness where (48%; 198) of the respondents strongly disagreed that family preference on a particular pathway and

choice of malaria treatment option influences the treatment of malaria illness, (7.25%; 29) of the respondents strongly agreed that family preference on a particular pathway and choice of malaria treatment option influences the treatment of malaria illness. This implies that the decision of the head or elder members of the family (significant other) is not final but depends on the perceived cultural description and available financial resources that will facilitate the health care service appropriate for the treatment of malaria illness.

As shown in the Table 4 above, (59.5%; 238) of the respondents strongly agreed that an individual's and significant other level of income affects the choice of an appropriate malaria illness treatment option in the study area, while (3%; 12) of them strongly disagreed to the influence of income in the treatment option of malaria illness in the study area. This indicates that a patient's level of income and that of their immediate caregivers determine the kind of treatment and pathway they are likely to go for in treating malaria illness in the study area.

From the above data as presented in Table 4, it is easy to deduce that factors such as cost of medication, proximity to healthcare facilities, cultural beliefs, and patient's level of income have a significant influence on the choice for appropriate malaria treatment in the study area.

Findings

Regarding objective one, which is to examine public responses to the influence of socio-economic status on malaria treatment in the Municipal Local Government Area of Kano State, the researchers found that the major socio-economic factors affecting prompt medical care included the cost of preferred medication based on respondents' income, proximity to healthcare services capable of providing treatment, existing cultural experiences with malaria episodes, perceptions and beliefs about the illness, and inaccessibility to prompt healthcare due to job constraints. These findings align with the studies of Munyeki et al. (2021), Thwing & Garbus (2014), and Owusu-Agyei et al. (2018). However, perceptions and beliefs regarding the nature of malaria illness and treatment were new in this study area, as these perceptions are reinforced by existing schemas from past malaria episodes in the community.

The theoretical framework used in this paper supports the previous discussion, where delays occur due to decision-making about the best available and affordable healthcare services for the victim of malaria and their significant other. As the results showed, this delay can be attributed to the income of the sick victim and their family, which affects the affordability of modern healthcare services. It can also be due to the distance needed to access healthcare and the perceptions about malaria illness and treatment, all of which contribute to delays in seeking care, as outlined by the three-delay model.

The second objective of this paper is to explore the various treatment options available for malaria in the study area. There are two main healthcare pathways: orthodox and traditional systems. However, many respondents practice medical pluralism, combining traditional and orthodox medicines. Factors such as cultural beliefs, personal

perceptions of the illness, availability and proximity of healthcare services, financial resources, and medication costs influence the choice of treatment for malaria in the area. This discussion aligns with the works of Julie et al. (2020) and Zakariyya (2023), who both identify medical pluralism as a pathway to healthcare.

The three-delay model also suggested, in line with previous findings, that the sick will definitely seek healthcare because of the ailment that has affected the body. The healthcare pathways identified in the study area included both orthodox and traditional options. However, most people in the area resort to using dual medication when seeking a cure.

The last objective of this paper is to investigate the possible factors influencing the choice of malaria treatment in the municipal local government area in Kano State. These factors, as investigated, include the cost of medication, ease of access to healthcare facilities, cultural beliefs, and patients' income levels, all of which significantly influence the choice of appropriate malaria treatment in the study area. These findings are consistent with the work of Birkhead et al. (2019); Mok et al. (2020); Munyeki et al. (2021). However, family preference is found to be insignificant in determining the choice of malaria treatment in the study area.

The theoretical framework used supported that factors such as income level, accessibility, means of transportation, and proximity to healthcare, among others, can contribute to additional delays in reaching the designated healthcare facility. As observed in the study area, the cost of medication, proximity and easy access to healthcare facilities, cultural beliefs, and the patient's income level greatly not only cause delays in reaching care but also affect the choice of care. This delay in making the most appropriate care is more problematic than just reaching the healthcare system.

In a nutshell, this paper was able to show that there is a delay in choosing appropriate care, which indicates a delay in accessing or using the necessary pathway to cure malaria. This specific delay—in the selection of the right treatment—is crucial for the overall treatment and potential eradication of malaria in the study area.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings in this study. First, delays in accessing care significantly hinder malaria treatment, mainly due to respondents' socio-economic factors such as their type of work, distance to health facilities, medication costs, and slow decision-making about where to seek care. Second, there are three main malaria treatment options available to the study population: orthodox, traditional, and dual medication. Finally, factors like medication costs, income levels, lay referrals, cultural beliefs, and lay knowledge are key influences on treatment choice—whether orthodox or traditional—causing additional delays in making perceived care decisions for malaria illness and treatment.

Recommendations

The following are recommendations based on the study's conclusions.

- i. First, there should be improved access to healthcare facilities by the government at all levels. Efforts should be made to increase the number of healthcare facilities in the Kano Municipal L.G.A. and to make them more accessible to all members of the community. This could involve setting up mobile health clinics to offer door-to-door treatment or offering transportation services to those who live far from healthcare centers.
- ii. Second, provision of financial assistance for malaria patients by the government and other non-governmental agencies to cushion the cost of medication. Given that cost is a major factor influencing treatment choices, it is important to provide financial assistance, such as subsidized medication, provision of routine malaria drugs for preventive care, free malaria treatments in public hospitals, and other orthodox healthcare levels and health insurance schemes, to make malaria treatment more affordable for all socio-economic groups.
- iii. Third, increase awareness and education to the populace on the dangers of malaria and the need for prompt and appropriate treatment. There is a need to educate the population on the importance of seeking prompt and appropriate treatment for malaria. This could involve community outreach programs, health education campaigns, and training local healthcare providers on dispelling myths and misconceptions about malaria treatment options.
- iv. Lastly, promote medical pluralism where people can easily access healthcare of their choice. Recognizing the prevalence of medical pluralism among the study population, efforts should be made by the municipal local government to integrate traditional healers into the formal healthcare system. This could involve training traditional healers on basic malaria treatment protocols, encouraging collaboration between traditional and modern healthcare providers, and fostering mutual respect and understanding between the two healthcare systems.

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